

Mixed ligand complexes of alkaline earth metals. Part-XIII. Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} complexes with 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde and β -diketones

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Reactions of Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} chlorides with 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde and β -diketones in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratios have resulted in the formation of mixed ligand complexes of the type [MLL'(H₂O)₂] (where M = Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} or Ba^{II}, HL = 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde and HL' = pentane-2,4-dione, 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione or 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione). These complexes have been characterized by elemental analyses, TLC, IR and ¹H NMR spectra.

In continuation of our earlier work on mixed ligand complexes of alkaline earth metals¹, in the present paper the mixed ligand complexes of the type [MLL'(H₂O)₂] (where M = Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} or Ba^{II}, HL = 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde (5-NO₂sal); HL' = pentane-2,4-dione (acetylacetone, acacH), 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione (benzoylacetone, bzacH) or 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione (dibenzoylmethane, dbzmH) are described.

Results and discussion

The reactions of the metal ions with 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde and pentane-2,4-dione, 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione or 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratios result in the formation of mixed ligand complexes of the type [MLL'(H₂O)₂].

The resulting mixed ligand complexes have been isolated as yellow solids (yield ~40–80%). All the complexes are insoluble in most of the organic solvents such as methanol, ethanol, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and *n*-hexane but soluble in DMF and DMSO. Most of these complexes decompose on heating at higher temperatures but [Mg(5-NO₂sal)(dbzm)(H₂O)₂] is sharp melting. The molar conductances of the complexes are very low indicating their non-electrolytic nature. Presence of two coordinated water molecules in the mixed ligand complexes of alkaline earth metals with similar ligands has been established by TGA studies². The characteristics and analyses of the complexes are recorded in Table 1. The metal atom appears to be hexa-coordinated in these complexes and the probable geometry may be octahedral³.

TLC of the mixed ligand complexes was performed on silica gel G using benzene petroleum ether (1 : 1) as a solvent. The complexes show a single spot having R_f values between the two corresponding symmetrical bis-complexes. This indicates that they are mixed complexes rather than a mixture of the two corresponding bis-complexes.

Infrared spectra :

In the IR spectra of the mixed ligand complexes bands at 1590–1600 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to $\nu_{C=O}$ and those at 1330–1350 cm⁻¹ to ν_{C-O} respectively. In free acetylacetone, bands at 1724 cm⁻¹ and 1608 cm⁻¹ have been reported due to $\nu_{C=O}$ and ν_{C-O} . In benzoylacetone, bands due to C=O and C–O have been reported at 1724 cm⁻¹ and 1600 cm⁻¹ respectively and in case of dibenzoylmethane C–O band has been reported to appear at 1600 cm⁻¹. Thus $\nu_{C=O}$ frequency of the β -diketone ligands is shifted to lower wave number side in the mixed ligand complexes supporting the chelation of the metal ion to the ligand moiety⁴. Such shifts to lower wave number side have been recorded in mixed ligand complexes of alkaline earth⁵ and transition metals⁴ with similar ligands. In the mixed ligand complexes, the weak bands in the region 400–550 cm⁻¹ which are absent in the free ligands, may be assigned to ν_{M-O} vibrations⁶.

Nuclear magnetic resonance spectra :

¹H NMR spectra of the mixed ligand complexes of Mg^{II} were recorded in DMSO-*d*₆ and spectrum of one representative complex [Mg(5-NO₂sal)(bzac)(H₂O)₂] is given in Fig. 1. In free 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde the aldehydic CH pro-

Table I. Analytical and physical data of the mixed ligand complexes

Compd.	Decomp. temp. (°C)	Analysis % : Found (Calcd.)			Metal
		C	H	N	
[Mg(5-NO ₂ sal)(acac)(H ₂ O) ₂]	300	44.03 (44.13)	4.79 (4.93)	4.04 (4.28)	7.31 (7.46)
[Mg(5-NO ₂ sal)(bzac)(H ₂ O) ₂]	195	52.25 (52.53)	4.38 (4.60)	3.02 (3.18)	6.23 (6.27)
[Mg(5-NO ₂ sal)(dbzm)(H ₂ O) ₂]	175 (m.p.)	58.36 (58.66)	4.28 (4.47)	3.01 (3.10)	5.28 (5.40)
[Ca(5-NO ₂ sal)(acac)(H ₂ O) ₂]	325	41.88 (42.00)	4.36 (4.70)	3.97 (4.09)	11.62 (11.74)
[Ca(5-NO ₂ sal)(bzac)(H ₂ O) ₂]	160	50.28 (50.50)	4.10 (4.40)	3.39 (3.46)	9.80 (9.93)
[Ca(5-NO ₂ sal)(dbzm)(H ₂ O) ₂]	300	56.32 (56.68)	4.06 (4.30)	2.78 (3.00)	8.52 (8.61)
[Sr(5-NO ₂ sal)(acac)(H ₂ O) ₂]	325	36.59 (36.96)	4.01 (4.13)	3.32 (3.59)	22.72 (22.53)
[Sr(5-NO ₂ sal)(bzac)(H ₂ O) ₂]	315	44.58 (45.00)	3.89 (4.01)	3.12 (3.09)	19.65 (19.43)
[Sr(5-NO ₂ sal)(dbzm)(H ₂ O) ₂]	275	56.79 (56.92)	4.12 (4.34)	2.96 (3.01)	17.19 (17.07)
[Ba(5-NO ₂ sal)(acac)(H ₂ O) ₂]	275	32.49 (32.78)	3.42 (3.64)	2.99 (3.18)	31.18 (31.31)
[Ba(5-NO ₂ sal)(bzac)(H ₂ O) ₂]	315	39.79 (40.00)	3.48 (3.60)	2.57 (2.79)	27.27 (27.43)
[Ba(5-NO ₂ sal)(dbzm)(H ₂ O) ₂]	275	46.52 (46.89)	3.34 (3.57)	2.18 (2.48)	24.62 (24.40)

Fig. 1. ¹H NMR spectrum of [Mg(5-NO₂sal)(bzac)(H₂O)₂].

ton gives a signal at δ 10.20 ppm which is shifted upfield in the mixed ligand complexes $[\text{Mg}(5\text{-NO}_2\text{sal})(\text{acac})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, $[\text{Mg}(5\text{-NO}_2\text{sal})(\text{bzac})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ and $[\text{Mg}(5\text{-NO}_2\text{sal})(\text{dbzm})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ and appears at δ 9.67, 9.83 and 9.71 ppm respectively. This confirms the coordination of the C=O group of the aldehyde moiety to the magnesium atom. In free acetylacetone, the resonances due to the CH_3 and CH protons have been reported at δ 1.99 and 5.54 ppm respectively⁷ which are shifted upfield (δ 1.77 and 5.10 ppm) in the complex $[\text{Mg}(5\text{-NO}_2\text{sal})(\text{acac})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$. Appearance of a single methyl resonance of the acetylacetone moiety in the mixed ligand complex confirms the octahedral structure in which two *trans* positions are occupied by two water molecules. In *cis* conformation two methyl resonances would have been observed⁷. In free benzoylacetone the resonances due to the CH_3 and CH protons have been reported at δ 2.19 and 6.18 ppm respectively⁷ which are shifted upfield (δ 1.92 and 5.94 ppm) in the mixed ligand complex $[\text{Mg}(5\text{-NO}_2\text{sal})(\text{bzac})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$. These upfield shifts confirm the coordination of the β -diketone ligands to the metal atom.

Experimental

Salicylaldehyde (E. Merck), 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde (Aldrich), pentane-2,4-dione (IDPL), 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione (Fluka), 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione (SD's) and ethanol were purified by distillation. $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck), $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck), $\text{SrCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck) and $\text{BaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck) were of A.R. grade.

Analytical methods : Magnesium, calcium and strontium were determined volumetrically by EDTA and barium gravimetrically as barium sulphate. Carbon and hydrogen analyses were carried out on a Heraeus Carlo Erba 1108 instrument and nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded in the region 400–4000 cm^{-1} on a Nicolet Magna-550 FT IR spectrophotometer. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ using TMS as a reference on a Bruker 300 and on a Jeol FX 90 Q FT NMR spectrometers.

Synthesis of mixed ligand complexes : To the ethanolic

solution of metal chloride (1.31 mmol in 1 ml of ethanol) an ethanolic solution of 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde (1.31 mmol in 1 ml of ethanol) and β -diketone (1.31 mmol in 1 ml of ethanol) were added. The pH of the resulting solution was raised to ~ 10 – 10.5 by adding 2% NaOH solution (~ 2 ml) dropwise with constant stirring. After stirring for 3–4 h the resulting yellow solid was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure.

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